

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Phishing detection by Transformers: Adversarial Robustness and Cross-Lingual Generalization

OPEN ACCESS

Received: 15/01/2026

Accepted: 28/03/2026

Published: 09/04/2026

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Citation: Apeke S, Djiraikinan T, Barate M (2026) Phishing detection by Transformers: Adversarial Robustness and Cross-Lingual Generalization. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(12): 851-860. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i12.51>

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Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: To evaluate cross-lingual performance and effectiveness against adversarial attacks. **Method:** this study fine-tuned four transformer models: BERT, RoBERTa, mBERT and XLM-RoBERTa. The proposed methodology involves training the models on the baseline data (English dataset G1) and then evaluating them on other data organized into four groups. **Findings:** Results revealed that the performance of RoBERTa and BERT collapses in cross-lingual transfer, whereas XLM-RoBERTa maintains its performance (93.43% versus 93.41% on the baseline). This suggests the benefit of the multilingual structure beyond the data. Furthermore, adversarial evaluation allowed to show that transformer models struggle to detect sophisticated phishing emails. Through adversarial training, the proposed method notably achieved a 6.54% increase in F1 Score for RoBERTa. **Novelty:** This study proposes that combining multilingual models with adversarial training ensures effectiveness against adversarial attacks while providing a high-performing multilingual system for phishing detection.

Keywords: Phishing; Cross-Lingual; Adversarial Robustness; Zero-shot transfer; Transformer

1 Introduction

Phishing is one of the most widespread and costly cyberattacks. These attacks have continued to evolve at the same pace as the evolution and performance of processors and artificial intelligence (AI). The negative consequences on the economies of companies, even individuals, are becoming frequent and significant. Several studies have been carried out on this topic, ranging from simplistic analysis to advanced AI-based detection methods. With the democratization of digital services, social networks and e-commerce, phishing attacks have grown exponentially, both in volume and sophistication. The Anti-Phishing Working Group (APWG) publishes quarterly reports with the number of observed phishing attacks, 4Q 2021: 316,747 attacks in December 2021, 2Q 2022: 1,097,811 attacks, 1Q 2023: 1,624,144 attacks, 2Q 2025: 1 130,393 attacks^{(1), (2), (3), (4)}, The Verizon Data Breach Investigations Report (DBIR) gives an overview of “breaches” (proven violations) and recalls the place of the human factor and phishing among the entry routes⁽⁵⁾. It should be noted that there has been a gradual

evolution in phishing detection methods. Traditional methods relied on blacklists, heuristic rules based on URLs, lexical and structural characteristics of web pages or emails^{(6), (7)}. These techniques are limited by their inability to detect zero-day attacks, by email obfuscation, and by the high rate of false positives. Advanced techniques based on Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) have appeared as a promising solution.

Over the last 5 years, deep learning approaches (CNN, LSTM) have shown strong potential for detecting phishing attacks. Despite these advances, several unresolved problems persist. Problems of excessive dependence on labeled data, semantic analysis of emails and web pages; Aljofey and al.⁽⁸⁾ used deep learning to detect phishing sites. They showed that CNNs can achieve accuracy over 95%. However, these models are unable to understand contextual semantics and generally require manual feature extraction^{(8), (9)}, lack of validation in a real context^{(10), (11)}, low robustness against adversarial attacks⁽¹²⁾.

The advent of Transformer architectures in 2017 paved the way for LLMs such as BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers)⁽¹³⁾ and RoBERTa (Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach)⁽¹⁴⁾, which have demonstrated excellent results on text classification tasks. Recent studies show that these models are capable of achieving up to 99% accuracy on phishing detection tasks^{(8), (15), (16)}. Gupta et al., 2024⁽¹⁷⁾ combined BERT with CNN for phishing detection and achieved 97.5% accuracy. Additionally, Farhan et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ compared three BERT-based models and confirmed results exceeding 98%.

However, a critical analysis of these results reveals unresolved challenges: Most of the literature focuses exclusively on evaluating monolingual models on English data, creating a cross-lingual validation gap. Furthermore, the advent of LLMs has introduced another challenge. Can models like BERT and RoBERTa maintain their performance when faced with sophisticated emails generated by other LLMs?

To fill this gap, this study proposes a framework based on multilingual evaluation and adversarial robustness: We demonstrated that multilingual models like XLM-RoBERTa perform better in cross-lingual transfer than monolingual models: XLM-RoBERTa achieves 93.43% F1 compared to 52.9% for RoBERTa. The introduction of adversarial training allowed us to improve the performance of the models, enhancing XLM-RoBERTa's results by 6.54 points.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data collection and description

The datasets used in this work come from 4 public sources: the Enron Email corpus (<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/naserabdullahalam/phishing-email-dataset?select=Enron.csv>), the SMS Spam Collection (<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/228/sms+spam+collection>), Phishing Email (<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/subhjournal/phishingemails>) and Email Spam Classification Dataset (<https://huggingface.co/datasets/UniqueData/email-spam-classification>) for phishing messages and spam. These sources have been selected for their diversity and public availability.

Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of these five data sources.

Table 1. Public corpora used as data sources

Source	Total size	Safe	Phishing
Enron Email	29 767	15 791	13 976
SMS Spam Coll.	5 574	4 827	747
Phishing (Kaggle)	18 650	11 322	7 328
Spam (HF)	84	42	42

2.2 Data preprocessing

The preparation of the dataset begins with grouping them into five groups. Group 1 serves as the baseline training and evaluation set, while group 2 is dedicated exclusively to adversarial evaluation. Figure 1 presents some examples of data generated for this latter group.

Groups 3 and 4 are used for cross-lingual evaluation. Group 3 comes from automatic translation (via google translate api), and group 4 originates from native generation with Ollama. Finally, group 5 were created for adversarial training. Table 2 presents these different data groups and the methods used to obtain them.

This structuring made it possible not only to organize the experiments carried out in this work but also to carry out the cleaning in two stages: automatic processing and manual qualitative validation.

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 Email 3
 =====
 “We are pleased to announce a strategic partnership with the National Ford Concessionary Program, offering a compelling 120-month financing plan to help you achieve your financial goals. This plan provides up to 90 days of credit per lance, with prizes and exclusive offers available each month. We offer a range of financing options, including credit for \$17.347 to \$67.990, and a significant monthly credit of \$31.384. Visit [link to website] to learn more and begin your journey to financial freedom.”

Longueur: 506 caractères | 80 mots

=====
 Email 4
 =====
 Expedite Media Group, Inc. is offering a complimentary web site analysis to help you assess your current online performance and identify opportunities for increased sales productivity. Our team will conduct a thorough review of your website, providing a data-driven effectiveness appraisal and actionable recommendations designed to enhance the user experience and drive conversions. We are committed to providing affordable access to the power of the internet and believe this analysis represents a significant investment in your online business growth. To learn more about this limited-time offer and schedule your assessment, please call us at (630) 876-8066 or visit our website at [Website Address].

Longueur: 705 caractères | 103 mots

Fig 1. Examples of adversarial phishing emails generated by Gemma 3:1B

Table 2. Composition of the five experimental groups

Group	Total	Safe	Phishing	Language	Method
G1 - Baseline	15000	8,288	6,712	EN	Public corpora
G2 - Adversarial	2,180	1,850	330	EN	Ollama generation
G3 - Translation	2,353	2000	353	FR	Google Translate
G4 - Generation	2,326	2000	326	FR	Ollama generation
G5 - Adv. Training	15,472	8,390	7,082	EN	Hybrid composition

2.3 Automatic cleaning

The first preparation phase involves performing a careful cleanup aimed at removing waste and inconsistencies without altering the meaning of the messages. This process includes four steps:

1. **Filtering of metadata and artifacts:** regular expressions were used to remove metadata and AI generation artifacts such as 'Subject:', 'Here is a phishing email...', 'Generated email:', etc. The goal is to retain only the content of the emails.
2. **Duplicate removal:** detection and removal of identical or nearly identical messages by MD5 hashing of the normalized content (lowercase, standardized spaces) to ensure corpus diversity and prevent over-fitting;

3. **Length validation:** After removing duplicates, outliers were cleaned up. Then, all incomplete or corrupted messages were eliminated, those containing fewer than 50 characters, and all very long messages exceeding the optimal processing capacity (more than 2000 characters).
4. **Structural consistency check:** Exclusion of empty messages containing only spaces or control characters, or displaying an obviously inconsistent structure like sequences of random characters.

2.4 Qualitative validation

To complete the automatic cleaning, qualitative analysis was conducted to ensure semantic consistency and preserve the malicious intent in the generated and translated emails. This validation is structured in 3 phases:

1. **Manual inspection:** This is the step during which random sample of 50 messages from each group (i.e., 7% for group 2 and 2% for groups 3 and 4) were extracted to verify linguistic consistency, the absence of AI generation artifacts, and the maintenance of phishing scenarios. This step also allows us to check that the emails in group 4 are properly written in natural language with appropriate phrasing.
2. **Lexical diversity analysis:** To ensure that the data includes truly diverse and difficult-to-detect emails, a similarity calculation between the generated emails and the original emails was done. With an acceptable similarity rate set at 0.5, the results gave a much lower rate (0.204), thus ensuring the diversity of emails. The tf-idf analysis result is shown in Figure 2.
3. **Baseline detectability test:** Finally, to ensure that generated emails are really more difficult to detect, an evaluation of simple BERT models on the generated data and then on the original emails was carried out. This phase made it possible to observe a difference in F1 score of 2% between the original emails and the generated emails.

Fig 2. Distribution of TF-IDF cosine similarity between adversarial and baseline emails

2.5 Modeling

During the modeling phase, four pre-trained Transformer models for email classification were refined: BERT-base-cased and RoBERTa-base for English, and bert-base-multilingual-cased (mBERT) and XLM-RoBERTa-base for multilingual evaluation. The main inputs of the proposed models are emails, which are textual data. To achieve a good balance between computational constraints and system performance, the basic versions of the proposed models were chosen (110-125M parameters).

2.5.1. Processing Pipeline and Model Architecture

BERT and its descendants, such as RoBERTa, rely exclusively on an encoder to learn the context of emails. The encoder processes the entire sequence simultaneously to understand the true meaning of the word being processed and its surrounding context. The process of classifying an email involves a processing chain that begins with tokenization and ends with a softmax that classifies emails as either phishing or legitimate. Figure 3 illustrates the phishing detection pipeline.

Fig 3. Pipeline for phishing detection using Transformer templates

Each encoder layer in this architecture combines a multi-headed self-attention mechanism and a feed-forward network, followed by residual connections and normalization. Self-attention establishes weighted relations between tokens via three representations (Query, Key, Value):

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \tag{1}$$

Where Q (queries), K (keys) and V (values) represent linear projections of the input, and d_k is the dimension of the keys (64 for BERT-base with 12 heads of attention). The factor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ stabilizes the gradients during learning. Multi-headed attention ($h = 12heads$) captures different types of linguistic relations that exist in an email:

$$\text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V) = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_{12}) W^O \tag{2}$$

Where $W^O \in R^{768 \times 768}$ represents the output projection matrix that combines the 12 heads of attention. The feed-forward position-wise network projects the embeddings of dimension 768 to 3,072, then back to 768:

$$\text{FFN}(x) = \text{GELU}(xW_1 + b_1) W_2 + b_2 \tag{3}$$

At the output of layer 12, the token representation [CLS] aggregates global semantic information. A linear layer followed by a sigmoid performs the binary classification:

$$\hat{y} = \sigma \left(W_{\text{cls}}, h_{[CLS]}^{12} + b_{\text{cls}} \right) \tag{4}$$

2.5.2. Configuration and training

During fine-tuning, models pre-trained for phishing detection were adapted via binary cross-entropy optimization:

$$L = \frac{-1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)] \quad (5)$$

AdamW optimizer was used with a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} . Training was carried out over 3 epochs with batch sizes of 16 and 32 and 500 warm-up steps. The model achieving the best F1 score on the validation set is kept for subsequent evaluation phases.

2.5.3. Evaluation protocol

Metrics

All metrics were defined from the confusion matrix: true positives (TP, phishing correctly detected), true negatives (TN, legitimate messages correctly classified), false positives (FP, legitimate phishing classified), and false negatives (FN, phishing not detected). The main metrics used to evaluate the performance of our models are **F1-Score**, **Recall** and **Accuracy**. Accuracy, although informative, is less of a priority in this security context.

Recall (sensitivity): measures the proportion of phishing detected:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (6)$$

Recall is the most critical metric: undetected phishing represents an unacceptable security risk.

F1-Score: represents the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall:

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (7)$$

where Precision $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$. Particularly well-suited to unbalanced data, the F1-Score is our main criterion for comparing models.

2.5.4. Experimental phases

Our evaluation protocol is structured into four complementary phases:

Phase 1 - Baseline: establishes the baseline performance of the BERT and RoBERTa models in detecting traditional phishing. This answers the question: What is the ability of transformers to detect traditional phishing?

Phase 2 - Adversarial robustness: tests baseline models against AI-generated phishing (Gemma3:1b) to answer the question: Do models trained on traditional phishing effectively detect sophisticated attacks generated by LLM? Degradation ($F1 = F1_{\text{baseline}} - F1_{\text{adversarial}}$) is used to quantify vulnerability.

Phase 3 - Cross-lingual generalization: This phase evaluates the **transfert zero-shot** English to French on translated corpus (Group 3) and natively generated corpus (Group 4). The aim is to answer two questions: (1) Do monolingual models (BERT/RoBERTa) effectively detect French phishing? (2) Can multilingual models (mBERT/XLM-RoBERTa) improve the cross-lingual generalization? This phase also compares the detection efficiency of translated versus natively generated emails.

Phase 4 - Solutions: explores **Adversarial training** as a possible solution to sophisticated attacks.

3 Results and Discussion

Presentation of the measured performance of the four Transformer models (**BERT-base**, **RoBERTa-base**, **mBERT**, **XLM-RoBERTa**) according to the three experimental axes proposed in this work: baseline performance in English, cross-lingual generalization to French, and robustness to adversarial attacks.

3.1 Performances Baseline (Group 1)

Table 3 presents the performances of the four transformers models on the baseline test set composed of 2,250 English samples (Group 1), including 1,913 legitimate emails and 337 phishing emails.

The results show that the pre-trained transformer models perform exceptionally well in detecting traditional phishing, with F1-scores ranging from 93.02% to 96.21%. RoBERTa stands out with an F1 score of 96.21%, while BERT and XLM-RoBERTa better identify phishing emails with a recall of 99.11%. These performances could be explained by the transformers' ability to understand the full context of an email and identify the relationship between two words, even if they are separated by several sentences. This low error rate (1.17% to 2.24%) observed is confirmed by the confusion matrices shown in Figure 4.

Table 3. Performance of models on English baseline test set (Group 1)

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
BERT	87.63%	99.11%	93.02%
RoBERTa	94.29%	98.21%	96.21%
mBERT	90.88%	97.92%	94.27%
XLM-RoBERTa	88.33%	99.11%	93.41%

Fig 4. Model confusion matrices on the baseline set test (Group 1)

3.2 Cross-Lingual Generalization (Groups 3 and 4)

This experiment evaluates the ability of the models to detect French phishing without any prior training in French (zero-shot transfer). Two French datasets were used for test:

- Group 3 (FR Translated): 2,353(2,000 legitimate and 353 phishing) emails translated via Google Translate API
- Group 4 (FR Generated): 2,326(2,000 legitimate and 326 phishing) phishing emails generated natively in French by Ollama/Gemma3:1b

a. Results on Translated Corpus (Group 3)

The performance of the zero-shot models on the French test set composed of phishing messages translated from English into French (2,353 samples, 15% phishing messages) is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Performances of models on translated French phishing (Group 3) - Zero-shot

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
BERT	39.89%	96.87%	56.84%
RoBERTa	83.94%	84.42%	84.18%
mBERT	91.42%	96.60%	93.94%
XLM-RoBERTa	89.90%	98.30%	93.91%

These results show that monolingual models (BERT-base and RoBERTa-base) suffer a performance collapse in zero-shot settings. On the F1 Score, BERT's performance dropped from 93.02% to 56.84%, a decrease of 36.18%. RoBERTa proves more resilient, with a drop of 12.03%. Unlike the monolingual models that collapse, the multilingual versions maintain good performance: mBERT loses only 0.33% of F1-score (94.27% → 93.94%), while XLM-RoBERTa shows a slight improvement of +0.5% (93.41% → 93.91%). Similarly, on other metrics, XLM-RoBERTa achieves the best performance with 98.30% recall and 89.90% precision. This cross-lingual robustness supports the hypothesis that multilingual pre-training enables effective generalization across languages.

b. Results on Generated Corpus (Group 4)

As with the translated data from Group 3, the performance of our models on Group 4 (natively generated) dropped drastically for the monolingual models. On the F1 score, XLM-RoBERTa reaches 93.43% and stands out as the best of the four models. Meanwhile, its monolingual version, RoBERTa, collapses completely with only 43.35% F1, a decrease of 52.26%. Surprisingly, although mBERT is multilingual, its F1 score dropped by more than 10 points, going from 94.27% initially to only 82.82% on the Group 4 dataset. The same trend was observed in other metrics: XLM-RoBERTa achieves the best results with 98.16% recall and 89.14% precision. These results demonstrate that XLM-RoBERTa offers the best performance in cross-lingual transfer on natively generated data as well as on translated data.

Beyond these results, a comparative analysis reveals that phishing generated directly in French is more difficult to detect than translated phishing. While XLM-RoBERTa remains almost stable, the results of the other models are lower on natively generated data than on translated data.

3.3 Robustness to Adversarial Attacks (Group 2 and 5)

a. Vulnerability to adversarial attacks

Models trained on traditional phishing (Group 1) were tested on AI-generated phishing (Group 2: Ollama Gemma3:1b). Table 5 shows the observed performance degradation.

All models experience a degradation in their performance when faced with AI attacks, with varying impacts depending on the architecture. Since the new emails are specifically generated to bypass traditional detection methods, the main metric becomes recall.

The results revealed that mBERT is the most vulnerable model against sophisticated phishing emails, with a recall of 89.09%, representing a drop of more than 8 points. XLM-RoBERTa also performs worse, with a decrease of 5.47 points; however, it remains generally close to RoBERTa and BERT, which have recalls of 93.33% and 96.36%, respectively.

As expected, the precision of the four models is almost intact. The smallest loss is observed for mBERT at -0.70 points, and the highest gain is on the side of RoBERTa with 0.19 points.

The drop in recall is particularly critical in this security context; the rate of false negatives (undetected phishing) becomes increasingly high with models like RoBERTa and mBERT.

Table 5. Performance degradation against IA adversarial attacks (Group 2)

Model	Test Set	Pre.	Recall	F1
BERT	Baseline	87.63%	99.11%	93.02%
	Adversarial	87.36%	96.36%	91.64%
RoBERTa	Baseline	94.29%	98.21%	96.21%
	Adversarial	94.48%	93.33%	93.90%
mBERT	Baseline	90.88%	97.92%	94.27%
	Adversarial	90.18%	89.09%	89.63%
XLM-RoBERTa	Baseline	88.33%	99.11%	93.41%
	Adversarial	87.78%	93.64%	90.62%

On the adversarial test set consisting of 330 AI-generated phishing emails, the models recorded respective false negative rates of 3.64% for BERT (12 undetected attempts), 6.67% for RoBERTa (22 attempts), 10.91% for mBERT (36 attempts), and 6.36% for XLM-RoBERTa (21 attempts). These rates confirm the emerging threat posed by large language models (LLMs) to cybersecurity: even with a lightweight model like Ollama Gemma3:1b (1 billion parameters), up to 1 in 10 phishing attacks can bypass current defenses. It was estimated in this work that more powerful models like GPT-5 or Claude 3 would be capable of generating emails that are more difficult for detection models to catch. Overall, this work made it possible to notice that thanks to specialized pre-training on a single language, monolingual models benefit from better semantic resolution. This allows them to more finely analyze adversarial attacks in English, whereas multilingual models experience a dilution of their capabilities when generalizing across multiple languages.

b. Performances with Adversarial Training

To resist adversarial attacks, the four models were retrained with 50% baseline data and 50% adversarial data, forming Group 5. These new models were tested with the adversarial data generated by Ollama/Gemma3:1b from Group 2. Table 6 shows the improvement provided by adversarial training on the models.

Table 6. Impact of adversarial training on robustness to AI attacks (Group 2)

Model	F1 Baseline	F1 Adv. (G2)	F1 Adv. Training	Improvement
BERT	93.02%	91.64%	96.67%	5.03%
RoBERTa	96.21%	93.90%	97.04%	3.14%
mBERT	94.27%	89.63%	95.61%	5.98%
XLM-RoBERTa	93.41%	90.62%	97.16%	6.54%

Adversarial training has improved model performance against adversarial attacks. On the F1 Score, XLM RoBERTa reaches 97.16%, an improvement of 6.54%. It is followed by RoBERTa (97.04%), while mBERT and BERT have lower results (95.61% and 96.67%, respectively). However, all models achieve over 95% F1 after adversarial training, demonstrating the effectiveness of this technique in strengthening robustness against AI-generated attacks. Indeed, the recall of all models has also increased, reaching over 98%.

3.4 Comparison of Proposed Model with Existing Works

A comparative analysis of our results with those of the literature was carried out. On the reference data, our RoBERTa model achieved an F1 score of 96.21%; this result is comparable to that of Jamal et al. (16), while remaining slightly lower than the performance obtained by Songailaite et al. (19) and Melendez et al. (9). Nevertheless, in line with these studies, our results showed that RoBERTa achieves better benchmark performance. Similarly, following the work of Diyasi et al., 2025 (20), the results showed that BERT can achieve an F1 score of 93.02% with a recall of 96.2%.

Regarding the issue of contradictory attacks, the click-through rate observed by Heiding et al., 2024 (21) in their work confirms our finding that generated contradictory emails are more difficult to detect. Furthermore, the results (98% accuracy) of the model we propose are superior to those reported in some more recent studies, such as Gholampour & Verma, 2023 (22) (94% accuracy), which use KNN for phishing email classification.

The uniqueness of our study lies in experimenting with the linguistic transfer capacity of models, which allowed us to identify XLM-RoBERTa as the model with excellent linguistic transfer capabilities. On the other hand, our adversarial tests confirm the difficulty that transformer models have in detecting sophisticated phishing generated by AI. This result aligns with Gholampour

and Verma (2023)'s⁽²²⁾ observations on the adversarial robustness of phishing detection models. Additionally, this study made available to the research community two datasets in French.

Finally, it should be noted that the majority of studies focus exclusively on monolingual models like BERT and RoBERTa without addressing their capacity for linguistic extension. Adversarial training as a means of circumventing adversarial attacks was also explored and yielded conclusive results.

4 Conclusion

In this study, phishing detection method based on the detection of adversarial attacks and cross-lingual generalization was proposed. The results confirm the effectiveness of Transformer models. Standard evaluation shows that BERT achieves 93.02% on the F1-Score, 96.21% for RoBERTa, 94.27% for mBERT, and 93.41% for XLM-RoBERTa. However, they remain highly vulnerable to AI-generated attacks. The results also showed that compared to generated emails, mBERT lost more than 8 points in performance, and XLM-RoBERTa lost 5.47 points. Furthermore, experiments revealed that monolingual models like BERT and RoBERTa have significant limitations in terms of multilingual generalization. To achieve robust performance against AI-generated attacks while ensuring multilingual capability, this work clarifies that it is necessary to combine multilingual models such as XLM-RoBERTa and mBERT with adversarial training.

This study has limitations that will need to be addressed in the next steps. The set of adversarial models used in this work comes exclusively from Gemma 3:1b. The next step is to combine several modern models such as GPT-4 or Claude 3.5 in order to create a sufficiently diverse dataset. As per Melendez's suggestion, we also plan to explore more lightweight models like distilBERT to make their deployment easier.

References

- 1) APWG report Q4 2021. 2021. Available from: https://docs.apwg.org/reports/apwg_trends_report_q4_2021.pdf.
- 2) APWG report Q2 2022. 2022. Available from: https://docs.apwg.org/reports/apwg_trends_report_q2_2022.pdf.
- 3) APWG report Q1 2023. 2023. Available from: https://docs.apwg.org/reports/apwg_trends_report_q1_2023.pdf.
- 4) apwg_trends_report_q2_2025_production. 2025. Available from: https://docs.apwg.org/reports/apwg_trends_report_q2_2025.pdf.
- 5) IBM Security and Ponemon Institute. Cost of a Data Breach Report 2024. 2024 Jul. Available from: <https://cdn.table.media/assets/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/30132828/Cost-of-a-Data-Breach-Report-2024.pdf>.
- 6) Sonowal G, Kuppusamy KS. PhiDMA – A phishing detection model with multi-filter approach. *J King Saud Univ - Comput Inf Sci*. 2020 Jan;32(1):99–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2017.07.005>.
- 7) Khonji M, Iraqi Y, Jones A. Phishing Detection: A Literature Survey. *IEEE Commun Surv Tutor*. 2013;15(4):2091–2121. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SURV.2013.032213.00009>.
- 8) Aljofey A, Jiang Q, Qu Q, Huang M, Niyigena JP. An Effective Phishing Detection Model Based on Character Level Convolutional Neural Network from URL. *Electronics*. 2020 Sep;9(9):1514. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics9091514>.
- 9) Meléndez R, Ptaszynski M, Fumito M. Comparative Investigation of Traditional Machine Learning Models and Transformer Models for Phishing Email Detection. *Computer Science and Mathematics*. 2024 Oct. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202410.1467.v1>.
- 10) Oest A, et al. Sunrise to Sunset: Analyzing the End-to-end Life Cycle and Effectiveness of Phishing Attacks at Scale. *USENIX Security Symposium*. 2020. Available from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Sunrise-to-Sunset%3A-Analyzing-the-End-to-end-Life-of-Oest-Zhang/ad9cd1b746bfd1248720efd58442a3803e94d158>.
- 11) Apruzzese G, et al. The Role of Machine Learning in Cybersecurity. *Digit Threats*. 2023 Mar;4(1):8:1–8:38. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3545574>.
- 12) (PDF) The Role of Machine Learning in Cybersecurity. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3545574>.
- 13) Devlin J, Chang MW, Lee K, Toutanova K. BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding. *arXiv*. 2018. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1810.04805>.
- 14) Liu Y, et al. Roberta: A robustly optimized BERT pretraining approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692*. 2019.
- 15) Almujaheed NF, Haq MA, Alshehri M. Comparative evaluation of machine learning algorithms for phishing site detection. *PeerJ Comput Sci*. 2024;10:e2131.
- 16) Jamal S, Wimmer H, Sarker IH. An improved transformer-based model for detecting phishing, spam and ham emails: A large language model approach. *Secur Priv*. 2024;7(5):e402. <https://doi.org/10.1002/spy2.402>.
- 17) Gupta BB, et al. Advanced BERT and CNN-Based Computational Model for Phishing Detection in Enterprise Systems. *CMES - Comput Model Eng Sci*. 2024;141(3):2165–2183. <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmescs.2024.056473>.
- 18) Farhan HA. Robust and Accurate Phishing Detection Using Enhanced DistilBERT: A Transformer-Based Approach. *J Al-Qadisiyah Comput Sci Math*. 2025 Sep;17(3):230–246. [10.29304/jqscm.2025.17.32403](https://doi.org/10.29304/jqscm.2025.17.32403).
- 19) Songailaitė M, Kankevičiūtė E, Zhyhun B, Mandravickaitė J. BERT-Based Models for Phishing Detection. Available from: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:266151752>.
- 20) Diyasi S, Ghosh A, Dey D. Cyber-Resilient Phishing Detection: BERT-Driven NLP for Advanced Email Security. *Int J HIT TRANSC ECCN Vol*. 2023;9(1A):8–20.
- 21) Heiding F, Schneider B, Vishwanath A, Bernstein J, Park PS. Devising and Detecting Phishing Emails Using Large Language Models. *IEEE Access*. 2024;12:42131–42146. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3375882>.
- 22) Gholampour PM, Verma RM. Adversarial robustness of phishing email detection models. *Proceedings of the 9th ACM International Workshop on Security and Privacy Analytics*. 2023;p. 67–76.